

THE INFLUENCE OF MOBILE DEVICES ON THE HEALTH OF YOUNG PEOPLE AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR REDUCING THEIR HARM

MOBIL QURILMALARNI O'SMIRLAR SOG'LIG'IGA TASIRI VA ULARNI ZARARLARINI KAMAYTIRISH BO'YISH TAVSIYALAR

ВЛИЯНИЕ МОБИЛЬНЫХ УСТРОЙСТВ НА ЗДОРОВЬЕ ПОДРОСТКОВ И РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ ПО СНИЖЕНИЮ ИХ ВРЕДА

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Abstract: *The article examines the positive and negative aspects of the interaction of teenagers with mobile devices, computers, and various gadgets. They show that excessive abuse of time spent communicating with gadgets has a negative impact on both the physical and mental health of adolescents. Recommendations are given on the use of mobile devices by adolescents and their reduction in harmful effects.*

Keywords: *gadgets, devices, adolescent health.*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada o'smirlarning mobil qurilmalar, kompyuterlar va turli xil gadjetlar bilan o'zaro munosabatlarning ijobiy va salbiy tomonlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Ular gadjetlar bilan muloqot qilish vaqtini haddan tashqari suiiste'mol qilish o'smirlarning ham jismoniy, ham ruhiy salomatligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishini ko'rsatadi. O'smirlarning modil qurilmalardan foydalanish va ularni zararli tasirlarini kamaytirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *gadjetlar, mobil qurilmalar, o'smirlar salomatligi.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматриваются положительные и отрицательные стороны взаимодействия подростков с мобильными устройствами, компьютерами, а также различными гаджетами. Показывают то, что чрезмерное злоупотребление временем общения с гаджетами отрицательно сказывается на состоянии как физического, так и психического здоровья подростков. Даются рекомендации по использованию мобильных устройств подростками и их снижению вредную влияние.*

Ключевые слова: *гаджеты, девайсы, здоровье подростков.*

The 21st century is the century of development of information technology and techniques. In this context, people cannot imagine their daily life without contact with various devices and gadgets, and of course, these devices can simplify human life and allow us to manage large flows of information and walk in harmony with life.

Let us first understand the concepts of these gadgets and mobile devices and how they differ from each other. Often, almost all electronic devices are called gadgets: phones, smartphones, computers, headphones, audio devices, etc.

However, if we look at this matter from a scientific point of view, a "gadget" (derived from the French word "*gâche*" - *a fastener, a fastener*) is a small device designed to facilitate and improve human life. These are devices without a power source (phone headsets, speakers, etc.), it is believed that the gadget cannot work independently without the main device, it only expands the functionality of the device.

A device ("*device*" - *means apparatus, device, tool*) is a small electronic device with power sources that can work without the help of other devices or gadgets. Classic examples of such devices are smartphones and laptops [1-2].

In modern society, there are also devices that combine the two concepts, which can work independently, but only fully work together with another device (smart watches and fitness trackers, etc.).

Modern teenagers communicate with this type of technology almost every day. They cannot imagine their lifestyle without the help of these miraculous devices: they listen to music, communicate virtually on social networks, measure blood pressure and heart rate, search for answers to questions they are interested in on various Internet pages. Of course, all this is very wonderful! But have any of our teenagers thought about how any gadgets can affect human health?

Many studies have been conducted to determine the impact of the computer on teenagers and children, they have determined the effects on the formation of the brain structure and mental health of the child during his development. Those who actively use various gadgets in everyday life develop faster and are able to divide attention and switch it when necessary. An improvement in verbal function is also noted, because communication on the Internet is very active. Experts say that the capabilities of gadgets also improve - fingers used to communicate on a tablet or phone move much faster than their peers who are far from gadgets [3-11].

The impact of gadgets on teenagers is also characterized by a decrease in concentration, which negatively affects persistence, quality of work and concentration. On the other hand, the abundance of new information and the ability to maneuver in its flows, identify unnecessary information, and quickly adapt to the modern environment. At present, the uniqueness of young people is that there are no clear boundaries between reality and the Internet world - they continue each other.

Of course, in this case, we will determine the pros and cons of these devices, because according to the World Health Organization, about 1.8 billion people around the world use smartphones every day. According to research, the average user checks their smartphone about 150 times a day. To clearly imagine this score, it is enough to observe the behavior of your peers in everyday life, think about your health and see the impact of gadgets and come to the necessary conclusion.

The advantages are that intelligent communication with gadgets allows us to develop intellectually: without leaving home, we can read books in any library, find information using search engines, learn a foreign language remotely, travel to countries and museums, etc. [5-7].

Using headphones allows us to listen to our favorite music without disturbing others, music helps to relax and relieve stress.

Remote communication with friends helps not to catch diseases during quarantine or bad weather (you can chat with friends without leaving home).

Fitness bracelets allow us to monitor the state of our body: we can see how much energy we spend, what our pulse and blood pressure are, what food we need to eat to stay in good shape.

Phones allow us to be aware of events related to our loved ones: our parents, our friends; by calling them we can be calm, free from anxiety and close at any moment. There are many advantages, but are there any disadvantages?

It turns out there are a lot of them.

A mobile phone is a mobile device that emits electromagnetic radiation. Magnetic storms can harm human health. Accurate measurements have shown that when receiving an incoming call, as well as when "hanging up" at the end of a

conversation, a field similar to a magnetic storm is observed around the device. The incident may affect the physical health of the cell phone owner. As a result of this, the following can be observed:

- mental diseases (increased excitability, indifference to the outside world, frequent mood swings, deterioration of the mastery index);
- occurrence of brain cancer;
- general deterioration of health;
- jump or vice versa - drop in blood pressure.

Mobile phone, tablet, e-book - constant contact with a mobile phone or tablet, for example, playing games or using the Internet, reading an e-book, causes eye fatigue. Also, the radiation from the screen causes deterioration of the function of the organs of vision. Uncomfortable posture while using a smartphone or mobile game console can lead to rapid fatigue, curvature of the spine and even bone diseases, including arthritis and arthrosis.

- deterioration of vision;
- diseases of movement organs and muscular system;
- diseases of the digestive organs, because the curvature of the spine disrupts the position of internal organs, including the stomach, liver, etc.

Headphones - if you listen to music through headphones for a long time, the eardrum can quickly weaken the tension without being able to withstand the constant direct impact of sound waves. In normal life, all the sounds around us are scattered and weakened by the atmosphere and distance. In headphones, the waves fall directly on the eardrum.

- Deterioration of hearing - leads to hearing loss.

Mobile phones, computers - According to Dr. Jonathan During, spokesman for the Royal College of Surgeons in Edinburgh, reduced physical activity leads to weight gain, which is the fourth leading cause of death worldwide [2].

- weight gain, which increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases.

Mobile phone - the cause of the disease is the constant use of the thumbs to type text on the smartphone, and it has been determined that the pain is the result of a

disease characterized by compression of the nerves passing through the wrist, swelling of tissues and damage to the musculoskeletal system. Mobile phones are simply covered with bacteria, which migrate to the body and cause various skin diseases.

- Blackberry thumb syndrome. Its main symptom is severe pain in the thumbs.
- acne and dermatitis.
- Erythema ab-igne is the appearance of chronic dermatitis caused by long-term heat exposure of the skin.

Communication on social networks - long-term communication on social networks causes a person to practically "disconnect" from the real world and live in a virtual world. He always needs to talk about himself and hear the approval and admiration of others. Such people always count the "likes" written to them, and when they receive "dislikes" they are very depressed.

- Narcissistic personality disorder.

Mobile phone Everyone who is in constant communication with the phone gets used to it, and "friend" is afraid to leave you. Gradually, such a connection leads to addiction (modilomania), which has a negative effect on teenagers. A person is like a drug addict, he constantly checks his phone and feels bad without it.

- nomophobia.
- nervousness, poor sleep, hallucinations.

The influence of modern gadgets on teenagers can be dangerous not only for their health, but also for their lives. "Death Squads" (known as "Blue Whales") encourage children to commit suicide. Of course, the cause of suicide is not the information of these groups, but its influence.

Messages in such chats, combined with the unstable psyche of teenagers and problems in the family or at school, force them to commit tragic acts. The harm of gadgets is their universality and direct access to any sites without the knowledge of adults. To prevent such changes, parents should monitor their child's activities on the Internet and control the content he sees.

How to identify gadget addiction? Parents should immediately notice changes in their children's behavior and interests. As a rule, adults often panic in vain, because a teenager is at the stage of personality formation and can change both his behavior and hobbies for certain topics. But there are also dangerous signs that indicate the dependence of modern teenagers on gadgets:

1. Problems with sleep and rest - staying on the phone or computer at night, the child does not sleep properly.
2. At home, not responding to adults' requests for help with household chores.
3. Ignoring the arguments of parents in the conversation about the impact of the computer on health. A teenager can argue, listen quietly, or even agree without changing anything in their behavior.
4. Physical fatigue: apathy, "bruises" under the eyes from lack of sleep, weakness.
5. Staying away from loved ones: closing the room, wanting to be alone.
6. Lost in situations without the Internet - not knowing what to do without gadgets.
7. Depressive states and lack of interest in real life.
8. Aggressive behavior when turning off the computer or taking away the gadget.
9. Emotional instability reminiscent of addiction. If the gadget is taken away, the child will stop communicating with loved ones. Psychological dependence on his favorite toy makes him promise to do even impossible things to get the phone or tablet back. At the same time, adults begin to have aggression, hysteria or panic attacks.

Fight against gadget addiction. Teenagers immersed in the world of digital technologies often face problems with their peers, teachers, relatives, members of the opposite sex, etc. in the real world. Unable to solve these difficulties themselves, children escape to virtual reality, where such conflicts do not exist or the solutions seem very simple. In this case, parents should seek help from qualified psychologists.

How to separate a teenager from gadgets without consulting a specialist? Make him interested and engage in communication. This should be done gradually, reducing the time you spend on the Internet to half an hour or an hour a day.

A one-time complete ban can have the opposite effect, because the desire for unattainable pleasure makes the child angry ("forbidden fruit seems sweet"). The best option is to limit the time with meaningful conversations between parents.

An alternative to virtual reality can be walking, going to the cinema, cafe or shopping center, riding a bicycle, rollerblades or a scooter. Everything that parents learned in childhood can be relevant for today's youth, the main thing is to separate them from the computer.

Thus, we see that the negative effects of gadgets on the health of teenagers are more than positive. In addition to the listed devices, you can find a lot of information about the effects of microwave ovens, routers, etc. What are the best ways to communicate with your favorite devices without damage?

- reduce the time of using your phone (modern devices have a special function - time limit);
- choose live communication with friends, walk more!
- consult experts or encyclopedias and reference books for advice and information.
- keep the phone away from your face when talking on the mobile phone.
- clean your smartphone, player, tablet or keyboard with disinfectants.
- do simple physical exercises, maintain proper posture when working at the computer for a long time.
- when listening to music through headphones, do not increase the volume above 80 decibels, think that those around you may not like your music selection.
- keep your devices as far away from you as possible when sleeping.

The effects of gadget addiction in teenagers are easier to prevent than to treat. This is not only emotional instability and a waste of time, but also prevents the emergence of diseases, their development and transition to chronic forms. Parents should take preventive measures at the first contact of the child with a computer or

phone - the time spent on the Internet should be less than playing sports, walking or communicating with friends.

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